

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Maritime Sector

by

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1. Drivers of Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Maritime Sector

The maritime sector is crucial to global trade and transportation, with maritime infrastructure serving as critical nodes in the international supply chain. Therefore, protecting maritime critical infrastructure is essential to safeguarding subjects such as economic prosperity, national security, environmental sustainability. Robust Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) measures are necessary in the maritime sector due to several key drivers impacting ports, ships, infrastructure and all the agents and systems that make up the port sector. The maritime sector, as a vital part of the global economy must be protected from a wide variety of threats that could disrupt the entire supply chain.

Prior discussions surrounding critical maritime infrastructure protection primarily centred on terrorist threats and were the main focus of concern, driven by the aftermath of the 11M or 9/11 terrorist attacks. [1] This focus began to shift towards cyber threats during the 2010s. Contemporary discourse emphasizes the growing importance of hybrid threats combining both physical and cyber threats, potentially involving deliberate actions undertaken by adversarial states [2].

Over the last decade, there have been countless examples of how an attack on critical maritime infrastructures can be a major threat to the safety and security of the maritime industry, and lead to disruption of port operations, leakage of critical data or complete cessation of activity. Examples of these threats include using cyberattacks to disrupt port operations while launching a physical attack on critical infrastructure or manipulating port control systems to cause navigational accidents with potential environmental consequences. The NotPetya cyberattack in 2017, which crippled operations at a major Ukrainian container terminal, and the GPS spoofing incident in 2020, which affected several ships in the Black Sea, are stark reminders of the evolving threat landscape facing the maritime sector.

The goal of maritime safety is to protect both physical assets encompassing vessels of all sizes, port facilities, data centres, cargo and personnel (crew, operators, and other stakeholders) against various types of physical threats e.g., intentional and unintentional incidents, dangers and harms such as physical disasters, storm at sea, fire, terrorism, social unrests, smuggling weapons and drugs, piracy. The goal of maritime cybersecurity is to ensure the confidentiality, integrity and availability of all cyber assets (e.g., telecoms, ICT, data, services) against cyber threats (e.g., phishing, spoofing, social

engineering (malicious activities using human interactions), masquerading identities, non-authorized access or distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks) [3].

In order to know the extent to which the maritime and port domain extends, Figure 1 shows these main assets which are present in most ports. Given the specific characteristics of each port, there will be different combinations of assets depending on the technological level as well as the different operations carried out in the port.

Figure 1: General maritime ports' assets (Drougkas, Sarri, Kyranoudi, & Zisi, 2019)

Building on this evolving understanding, European research projects like SAURON (Scalable multidimensional situation awareness solution for protecting European ports) [4] and PRAETORIAN (Protection of Critical Infrastructures from advanced combined cyber and physical threats) [5] have analysed and documented the state-of-the-art in CIP for the maritime sector. These

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projects have provided valuable insights into the vulnerabilities of port operations and potential mitigation strategies in the face of physical, cyber and hybrid threats, helping to increase the security and resilience of European CIs.

Thus, the development path of CIP in the maritime sector is marked by all these drivers:

- **Economic Significance**

The maritime sector is the backbone of global trade, accounting for approximately 90% of world trade by volume [6]. Within this context, European ports are a key artery for EU and global trade, with 74 % of goods entering or leaving the EU by sea [7]. Ports serve as vital gateways for the import and export of goods, contributing significantly to national and regional economies. Disruptions to maritime infrastructure, such as port closures or disruptions in shipping lanes, can have severe economic repercussions, impacting supply chains, commerce, and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Any disruption could have a devastating effect on the world economy and shake the economic integrity of EU member states.

- **National Security Imperatives**

Maritime critical infrastructure, including ports, terminals, vessels and maritime communication networks, are essential for national security and defence. These assets are vulnerable to physical attacks, cyber threats, maritime piracy, etc., which pose risks to maritime security, territorial integrity and maritime domain awareness.

- **Cybersecurity Risks**

The digitalisation and automation of maritime systems and processes have introduced new cybersecurity risks and vulnerabilities that appear due to increased reliance on interconnected systems for navigation, cargo management and vessel operations. Maritime Critical Infrastructure (CI), including vessel navigation systems, port operations and maritime communication networks, are susceptible to cyber threats such as malware, ransomware and supply chain attacks that could cause severe disruptions due to their dependence on all these new digital procedures. Targeted and untargeted attacks, using different attack vectors such as phishing, watering hole attacks, ransomware, malware, spoofing, and more, pose significant threats to maritime CI. These attacks exploit vulnerabilities in interconnected systems, potentially leading to disruptions in vessel operations, cargo management and port activities.

According to surveys on the shipping industry [8], the impact of these cybersecurity risks supposed a loss of corporate data (48%), disruptions in IT systems functionalities (67%), financial loss (21%) and affected the shipborne system functionalities (4%). Protecting maritime infrastructure against cyber threats is crucial for ensuring the reliability, safety and security of maritime operations.

- **Hybrid Threats**

Due to their interconnected and global nature, maritime CIs are vulnerable to hybrid threats that are rising over the last years. Hybrid tactics such as cyber-attacks on port facilities, maritime surveillance systems and shipping logistics networks combined with physical disruptions can interrupt maritime operations, compromise maritime security and undermine public trust in maritime infrastructure. Hybrid threats are characterised by the combination of conventional and non-conventional tactics employed by state and non-state actors to achieve strategic objectives. The maritime domain is particularly vulnerable to hybrid threats due to its vastness, interconnectedness, and strategic significance for global trade and security. The sabotage of the Nord Stream gas pipeline in September

2022, destroying the energy pipeline within the economic zones of Denmark and Sweden, and whose authorship is still under investigation [9], or the increased Russian activity aimed at reconnaissance of seaports, pipelines, fibre-optic cables, oil platforms and wind farms have been some of the most recent events that have put the spotlight on hybrid threats. One of the goals of these hybrid threats to maritime CIs is to undermine the economies of EU and NATO countries and directly affect the integrity of their security and competitiveness.

- **Environmental Protection**

The maritime sector is intricately linked to environmental sustainability, with maritime infrastructure playing a crucial role in preventing and responding to maritime pollution, oil spills and ecological disasters. Protecting maritime critical infrastructure is essential for preserving marine ecosystems, biodiversity, and coastal communities.

- **Regulatory Compliance**

Compliance with international maritime security regulations, such as the International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code, is essential for safeguarding maritime critical infrastructure. Ports and maritime stakeholders are required to implement security measures and procedures to prevent security incidents and respond effectively to security threats. Ensuring regulatory compliance is crucial for enhancing the resilience of maritime infrastructure and establishing common ground on maritime security standards.

2. Challenges and Limitations

To address the risks, the sector is undergoing a gradual adaptation to a new information technology landscape (encompassing data creation, processing, storage...). This involves integrating operational technologies to streamline and optimise current management processes. However, compared to other industries, shipping companies are adopting these advancements at a slower pace [10].

Several factors contribute to the slower adoption of new technologies in the maritime sector. Firstly, the inherent conservatism of this industry prioritises proven methods and rigorous safety testing before widespread implementation. Secondly, the global and fragmented nature of the industry, with diverse ownership structures and regulations that vary extensively from country to country and even from port to port, creates challenges in standardising technology adoption. Additionally, the physical constraints of operating vessels at sea, with limited and often unreliable connectivity, pose logistical hurdles for integrating real-time technologies. Furthermore, the historically skilled but aging workforce may require significant training and upskilling to effectively utilize these new tools. Managing these challenges is crucial to ensure the maritime sector remains resilient against hybrid and cyber threats and maintains its role as a secure and efficient pillar of the global economy.

Challenge 1: Emergence of new threats due to the digitalisation process of the ports

The integration of digital technologies and systems into port operations over the last years has expanded the attack surface, making ports vulnerable to threats such as malware, ransomware or phishing attacks. The application of all the new systems related with utilisation of cutting-edge Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) technologies that digitalise processes is usually disconnected from the prevention plans for potential CIP risks, making them vulnerable to being exposed. Attackers can target port systems, including cargo management systems, vessel navigation systems, and port communication networks to disrupt operations, steal and leak sensitive data or cause financial harm.

The evolution of the different threats for maritime CIs is closely correlated with the integration of these new processes, also increasing in both scale and complexity.

The convergence of Operational Technology (OT) and Information Technology (IT) systems in maritime environments introduces unique risks that arise from the adoption of this digitalisation process. OT systems, including industrial control systems (ICS), supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems and container handling equipment are increasingly connected to IT networks for data exchange and remote monitoring. However, this union exposes OT systems to cyber as well as hybrid threats and operational disruptions, posing risks to port operations, safety of the operations and even the personnel of the ports and vessels.

Challenge 2: Lack of Standardization in Port Cybersecurity Plans

There are many different kinds of port plans for cybersecurity, e.g. incident response plans (including cybersecurity), cybersecurity plans, business continuity plans (including cybersecurity), etc. which made port responses more difficult. Port cybersecurity plans are not standardised and concerns were expressed that they might have inconsistencies or gaps which may cause significant challenges if combined cyber and physical security attacks are mounted against ports and different security problems need to be considered together [11].

Challenge 3: Fragmented Operator Training and Response

Current training programs for maritime CIP personnel often suffer from a siloed approach, separating physical security and cybersecurity domains. This fragmentation hinders effective response to hybrid threats that combine cyber and physical attacks. This leads to a lack of multidisciplinary hybrid threat training.

Challenge 4: Public-Private Partnership (PPP) and Regulation

There is a disconnect between who regulates critical infrastructure (CI) and who owns it. Public entities are legally responsible for safeguarding CI, but a significant portion is owned, operated, and managed by private companies. This can lead to confusion about who's ultimately in charge. On one hand, government authorities overseeing maritime activities are responsible for ensuring reliable CI services. However, they lack the direct authority, resources, or expertise to fully guarantee CI integrity [12].

However, the complexities of PPP and regulation poses significant challenges for maritime CIP efforts. Such a challenge is, that sharing of information among public and private sectors tends to be slow-paced due to differences in priorities, and the private sector might be reluctant to share sensitive information due to confidentiality and strategic relevance of their operations. Furthermore, compliance with regulations can be complex and resource-intensive for private sector stakeholders. The public sector may provide funding and support for maritime CIP, while private sector stakeholders bear financial responsibility in security, technology upgrades, training programs, etc.

Challenge 5: Limiting and regulating the influence of external actors in order to maintain a competitive position for EU ports

EU ports heavily rely on foreign investment and partnerships due to the global nature of maritime trade. Although this can promote economic growth, it also raises concerns about potential vulnerabilities. Port operations may be influenced by external actors, such as state-owned enterprises

or private companies, whose objectives may interfere with and attack the integrity of the logistics chain in EU ports, affecting security protocols and decision-making processes.

Challenge 6: Complex Operating Environment

The maritime sector operates within a complex and dynamic environment characterised by vast distances, diverse stakeholders and varying regulatory frameworks and might be drastically different between countries. The wide variety of third-party service providers, the ship diversity (with its own systems, requirements, security procedures) and non-standardised communication protocols [13] are some of the characteristics that make the maritime domain a remarkably complex operational field where new challenges are constantly emerging. Coordinating security efforts across maritime borders, jurisdictions and sectors presents challenges for CIP planning, implementation and enforcement.

3. Solution Guidelines: Towards new CIP Capabilities and Resilience

In order to meet the challenges faced by the maritime sector, which is also constantly growing in complexity and scale, the maritime sector needs to take a number of measures to respond to these challenges and needs to proactively respond to potential issues that may affect the integrity of CIs. For this purpose, action guidelines are presented below to provide guidance on how to deal with these challenges.

3.1. Technical and Technological Guidelines

Guideline 1: Improving Cybersecurity Posture:

Improving cybersecurity posture requires a multi-layered approach that includes perimeter defence, network segmentation, endpoint protection and continuous monitoring. By implementing robust cybersecurity measures, such as firewalls, antivirus software, encryption protocols, and security awareness training programs, maritime stakeholders can mitigate cyber risks, safeguard sensitive data and protect critical infrastructure against cyber threats.

Guideline 2: Implementing Cyber Situational Awareness (CSA) and Hybrid Situational Awareness (HSA) systems

As port operators are responsible for running highly technical industrial systems and a wide range of interconnectivity networks as well as complex data centres while facing the need to manage the growing physical assets in the port environment, it is crucial to know what is happening at the port at any time.

By a continuous analysis of port data, CSA systems can identify anomalies and suspicious activity that might indicate a potential cyberattack in its early stages. In addition, the HSA combines information coming from the physical as well as from the cyber domain and is able to identify potential cascading effects of an incident [14]. By leveraging analysis with both CSA systems and combining physical and cyber domain information with HSA, port operators can gain a comprehensive understanding of their environment and proactively address potential security threats.

Guideline 3: Follow Maritime Security Management Plans

Maritime Security plans are an essential tool for mitigating risks and ensuring the integrity of maritime assets. Following the guidelines outlined by the Baltic and International Maritime Council

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(BIMCO) [15] provides a practical framework for developing and implementing an appropriate management plan of a maritime CI to cover physical, cyber and hybrid threats [3].

- 1) Identify each asset and assign ownership to responsible person(s).
- 2) Create a dynamic inventory of assets that is regularly updated and includes ownership information.
- 3) Categorise and classify assets based on their value (importance for the maritime CI), importance in the overall maritime ecosystem, and type (physical, cyber, user, procedures).
- 4) Identify the threat landscape and attack surface of each asset.
- 5) Select a risk assessment methodology, such as one from ENISA's inventory, and use it to estimate the risks.
- 6) Implement measures to protect assets using published lists of controls, such as ISO 27002, NIST 2020, SANS Top 20, and CIs good practices. Develop a risk treatment plan, including a contingency plan.
- 7) Develop a security policy that outlines how assets will be managed, protected, and distributed within the organization. Utilize existing guidelines such as ISPS, BIMCO, or ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1 (11/2001).
- 8) Continuously identify new threats and incidents, assess risks, determine ownership of CI assets, evaluate the strength of controls and manage incidents.

Guideline 4: Adopt Emerging Solutions

There is no free-risk maritime environment. This means that new problems and new risks are continuously emerging, regardless of the level of CI security that is present. In order to bring critical port infrastructures closer to an environment where risks are minimised as much as possible, new technologies and emerging processes are required to mitigate problems. In parallel, these new technologies must be subject of a potential risk analysis and kept up to date with the latest developments. New technologies will play a pivotal role in mitigating cyber and hybrid threats, ensuring increased defence.

Guideline 5: Establishing Secure Remote Access

Establish secure remote access mechanisms for maritime personnel, contractors, and stakeholders to access critical infrastructure systems and data remotely. Utilise virtual private networks (VPNs), multi-factor authentication (MFA) and session logging to authenticate users, encrypt communications and monitor access activities to prevent unauthorized access and data breaches.

Guideline 6: Enhancing Network Security

Strengthen network security measures by implementing robust firewalls, encryption protocols and access controls to safeguard maritime communication networks and data transmissions. Segment networks to isolate critical infrastructure assets, limit lateral movement of cyber threats and mitigate the impact of security incidents on maritime operations.

3.2. Regulatory Support Guidelines

Guideline 7: Enhancing Regulatory Compliance in Maritime CIP

The ISPS Code [16], established by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) [17] in response to the 9/11 terrorist attacks, serves as a crucial driver for regulatory compliance inside the maritime sector. The ISPS Code mandates ship owners and operators to co-operate and conduct ship security

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analysis, prevent security incidents and mitigate threats in maritime operations. The code consists of two parts with mandatory requirements and guidelines for ship and port facility security. Part A contains mandatory requirements and Part B contains implementation recommendations to enhance security. As concerns regarding cybersecurity in the maritime sector have escalated in recent years, the IMO has taken proactive measures to address cyber risks by implementing regulations and providing guidelines for industry professionals forcing them to adapt to these regulations.

The IMO recognises cyber risks in the maritime sector as the potential threats to technological assets, leading to failures in transport operations, cargo handling, and security systems due to virus attacks. While risk management has traditionally focused on physical security regulated by the ISPS Code, the IMO advocates for cybersecurity risk management through an approach based on five functional elements: identify, protect, detect, respond, and recover.

In collaboration with industry stakeholders such as BIMCO, the Cruise Lines International Association (CLIA) or the International Chamber of Shipping (ICS) the IMO published a guide in 2016 to address cyber risks in the maritime sector. This guide emphasizes the importance of conducting risk assessments as recommended by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) of the United States Department of Commerce. Furthermore, the guide follows the ISO 27001 standard for cybersecurity management, which is part of the ISO 27000 group on cybersecurity. By leveraging frameworks, maritime stakeholders can enhance regulatory compliance, mitigate cyber risks and ensure the safety and security of maritime operations and CIs.

Compliance with the mentioned regulatory frameworks is essential for safeguarding maritime CIs, maintaining operational continuity and preserving the integrity of the global maritime supply chain.

3.3. Training, Reskilling and Upskilling Guidelines

Guideline 8: PPP Investing in Training and Capacity Building

Investing in training and capacity building programs for maritime stakeholders is essential for enhancing security awareness, building technical expertise, and promoting a culture of security resilience. PPP can support training initiatives, workshops and exercises focused on security good practices, threat recognition, and incident response, thereby enhancing the readiness and capabilities of maritime stakeholders to address security challenges effectively.

Guideline 9: Develop Training Programs

Developing comprehensive training programs for maritime personnel, port operators, and industry professionals on cybersecurity good practices, threat recognition, incident response procedures and regulatory compliance requirements. Based on the recommendations of bodies like ISPS, it is suggested that all maritime personnel should carry out training, either at full scale simulations between the different teams or combining other response exercises to critical emergency situations. It is also recommended that such a training takes place at least once per year and with less than 18 months between the training activities [18].

3.4. Collaboration Guidelines

Guideline 10: Fostering Multilateral Cooperation

Fostering multilateral cooperation and partnerships among maritime stakeholders, regional organizations and international alliances is essential for addressing threats of maritime CI. Collaborative efforts can enhance information sharing, promote joint exercises and training and facilitate coordinated responses to CI threats, enhancing maritime security and stability.

Guideline 11: Leveraging Threat Intelligence Sharing

Participating in threat intelligence sharing initiatives and information sharing networks allows to exchange actionable threat intelligence, indicators of compromise and situational awareness data with industry peers, government agencies, and cybersecurity organizations. Collaborating on joint threat assessments, incident response coordination, and threat hunting activities will enhance collective defence against cyber threats in the maritime sector.

4. EU-CIP Recommendations for R&I Activities and Roadmaps

Some recommendations for enhancing maritime CIP are given in the following.

Recommendation 1: Adopt Risk-Based Approach

Implement a risk-based approach to cybersecurity, conducting regular risk assessments, threat intelligence analysis and vulnerability scanning to identify and prioritize security risks in maritime critical infrastructure. By assessing the likelihood and potential impact of cyber threats, maritime stakeholders can allocate resources effectively and implement targeted security measures to mitigate risks.

Recommendation 2: Build Detection and Correction Procedures for Threats of Maritime CI

Develop and implement robust detection and correction procedures for identifying and mitigating threats to maritime critical infrastructure. Establish continuous monitoring mechanisms, threat detection systems, and anomaly detection algorithms to identify suspicious activities, unauthorized access attempts, and security breaches in maritime networks and systems.

Implement automated response mechanisms, incident response playbooks and mitigation procedures to promptly address security incidents, minimize impact and restore normal operations following cyber, hybrid or other security threats at the maritime CIs.

Recommendation 3: Backup and Data Recovery

As port and port facility do implement backup policies, which describe all backup activities, and define the backup frequency. Identify the roles, responsibilities and authorities of individuals responsible for backup activities in the policies. Identify where and how the backups are stored.

Consider implementing the following good practices [19]:

- Back up all information and test backups – Create, manage, and regularly test backup efforts, ensuring copies of data, software and system images are consistent with cybersecurity policies.

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- Protect backup storage facilities – Identify all backup equipment or software needed to restore key functions and ensure all storage areas (e.g., lockers/closets) have appropriate security, such as locks, and environmental controls, such as dehumidifiers or water-resistant closures, to protect electronic equipment. Backups should be retained off-site (at an alternate facility if possible) and if necessary stored offline.
- Encrypt data in transit – Use software to protect data in transit through encryption.
- Encrypt backup data – Encrypt all backups. Create multiple backups so that, in the event of a breach, restoration can be performed with a version predating the infection.
- Consider the cloud – Cloud storage costs continue to drop and are a viable option for ports and port facilities seeking cost savings while realizing enhanced network scalability and availability. Ensure the cloud solution provides sufficient security measures.
- Establish redundancies – Ensure redundancies are established for key IT, OT and IIoT systems, Identify safety, security, and operational needs for systems with high-availability requirements.
- Train and exercise – Train staff to engage manual processes for re-establishing critical operations. Exercise recovery plans for cyber incidents compromising IT, OT and/or IIoT systems.

Recommendation 4: Conduct Audits and Periodic Risk Assessment

Port operators should conduct regular risk assessments and audits of their cybersecurity measures, including third-party risk audits of companies that operate in their port ecosystem. This involves identifying and assessing potential vulnerabilities, evaluating the effectiveness of existing security controls and prioritising areas for improvement. Stakeholders should implement targeted cybersecurity measures to protect their operations, systems and data by understanding their unique risk environment [20].

By evaluating these risks, vulnerabilities and potential consequences, maritime stakeholders can develop targeted mitigation strategies, allocate resources effectively and ensure through audits that they are aligned with regulatory compliance.

Recommendation 5: Investment in Training

Companies operating within the port perimeter should prioritize cybersecurity training and awareness programs for their employees and contractors. Training should cover topics such as identifying phishing emails, recognizing social engineering techniques, and reporting suspicious activities. Regular awareness campaigns that simulate phishing exercises and ongoing education will help create a security-conscious workforce that actively contributes to a company's cybersecurity defences.

Recommendation 6: Conduct Offensive Red Team Exercises

Conduct exercises to assess the effectiveness of maritime security controls, identify weaknesses and improve resilience against adversarial threats, combining all of these with a hybrid approach. Engage independent external security experts to simulate real-world attack scenarios, penetration testing and social engineering tactics to evaluate the effectiveness of security measures, response procedures and personnel readiness. Use red team findings to prioritise security improvements, address vulnerabilities and strengthen defence-in-depth strategies in maritime critical infrastructure.

5. The role of the EU-CIP project

EU-CIP plays a central role in promoting the security, resilience, and innovation of critical infrastructures. The mission of EU-CIP includes strengthening Europe's analytical capacities, amplifying the effects of research and innovation (R&I) endeavours, and building a strong ecosystem that links and facilitates stakeholders throughout the EU. In order to facilitate the implementation of guidelines and recommendations outlined above, the EU-CIP's coordination and support activities provide valuable assistance.

1. Enhancing Europe's Analytical Capabilities (EU-CIP-ANALYSIS)

- **Addressing New Threats and Market Dynamics:** The maritime sector is experiencing a paradigm shift driven by the emergence of new threats, particularly hybrid threats, and rapid market dynamics. This includes increased digitalization, automation, and connectivity, as well as the growing demand for sustainable shipping practices. EU-CIP's structured approach to collecting and analysing information about resilient infrastructures can provide crucial insights and foresight into these evolving threats and market needs. By leveraging EU-CIP's analytical capabilities, the maritime sector can anticipate and prepare for future challenges more effectively, ensuring the resilience and security of maritime critical infrastructure.
- **Supporting Port and Maritime Infrastructure Protection:** The whitepaper emphasizes the vulnerabilities of port and maritime infrastructure to a wide range of threats, including physical, cyber, and hybrid attacks. EU-CIP's analytical capabilities, including its observatory of CIP/CIR research outcomes, technologies, policies, and standards, can provide valuable intelligence and good practices to enhance the protection of these critical maritime infrastructures. By leveraging EU-CIP's insights and recommendations, stakeholders in the maritime sector can develop robust security measures, improve incident response capabilities, and ensure the continuity of maritime operations in the face of evolving threats.

2. Amplifying the Impact of R&I CIP/CIR Activities (EU-CIP-AMPLIFY)

- **Innovation in Ground Station Technology:** As the maritime sector evolves to address emerging threats and challenges, there is a growing need for innovative security technologies and solutions. EU-CIP's support services can play a crucial role in driving innovation in maritime security technology. By identifying gaps in existing solutions and areas with significant innovation potential, EU-CIP can help accelerate the development and commercialization of advanced security technologies for protecting maritime critical infrastructure. This includes technologies such as intrusion detection systems, surveillance cameras, access control systems, and cybersecurity solutions tailored to the unique needs of the maritime sector.
- **Validating and Commercializing Maritime Innovations:** EU-CIP provides a virtualized testbed for experimenting with standards-based CIP/CIR solutions and certification schemes, which is particularly relevant for the maritime sector. With its high R&D costs and critical need for reliable and validated technologies, the maritime sector can benefit from EU-CIP's support in validating and commercializing maritime innovations. By leveraging EU-CIP's knowledge about testbeds and certification schemes, maritime stakeholders can accelerate the adoption of innovative solutions, improve security resilience, and ensure the long-term sustainability.

3. Establishing a Vibrant Ecosystem (EU-CIP-ECOSYSTEM)

- **Promoting Cooperation in the Maritime Sector:** The whitepaper emphasizes how stakeholders must work together to overcome the different gaps of the sector. This requirement is met by EU-CIP's goal of creating a Knowledge-Hub and creating a community around its analytical services and innovation support services. This initiative fosters knowledge exchange, teamwork and a cohesive strategy for addressing the issues facing the maritime industry.

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- **Participation in Standard and Policy Development:** The whitepaper emphasizes the value of regulatory backing and the unification of international maritime practices and technology. By fostering the participation of pertinent parties in policy formation and standardization initiatives, EU-CIP's ecosystem approach and active dissemination and communication strategy can guarantee that the demands and difficulties of the maritime industry are suitably addressed and supported at the policy level.

The EU-CIP's coordination and support initiatives are aligned with the maritime sector's unique requirements and policies, as delineated in the whitepaper. Through strengthening Europe's analytical capacities, increasing the influence of research and innovation endeavours, and creating a dynamic environment, EU-CIP not only facilitates but also drives the maritime industry toward more creativity, adaptability and readiness to confront its distinct obstacles.

Through the integration of its coordination and support functions, EU-CIP makes a substantial contribution to the maritime industry by enhancing its analytical capacities, increasing the effect of research and development endeavours and creating a robust and interdependent ecosystem. This all-encompassing strategy is essential for encouraging innovation, guaranteeing the safety and robustness of port infrastructures and assisting with the application of the policies and suggestions delineated in the maritime industry whitepaper [21].

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